

Terpenoids. Part : LXXXVI. Synthesis of *trans*-8-Methylene-10-methyl-2-isopropylidene-decalin

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Selina-4(14),7(11)-diene, the title compound has been synthesised from *trans*-8-Methylene-10-Methyl-2-decalone(II) through a four steps procedure. Modified Wittig reaction with ethyl α -diethyl-phosphonopropionate on the decalone(II) gives the conjugated ester (III) which on lithium aluminium hydride reduction yields the allylic alcohol(IV). Conversion of the carbinol(IV) to *trans*-8-Methylene-10-methyl-2-isopropylidene-decalin(I) has been achieved through direct hydrogenolysis with sodium-ethanol in liquid ammonia as well as through bromide formation followed by the reduction of the bromide(V) using sodium borohydride in DMSO.

SELINA-4(14),7(11)-DIENE(I)* is an important naturally occurring compound among the many derivatives of eudesmane group of sesquiterpenes and has recently been isolated by Buttery and associates¹ from hop oil of European Gerberg variety.

Trans ring fusion of (I)¹ was established by the correlation with β -selinene (Ia) whose stereochemistry has been well established². The starting material, *trans*-8-methylene-10-methyl-2-decalone(II) in the projected synthesis was prepared using the method

of Marshall³. This methylene ketone was further tailored to achieve the synthesis of the title compound through a four step sequence (chart 1) involving the use of modified Wittig reaction to fix the position of the isopropylidene group. The methylene ketone (II) was submitted to the modified Wittig reaction⁴ with ethyl α -diethylphosphonopropionate in the presence of sodium hydride using dimethyl ether of diethylene glycol as solvent when *trans*-8-methylene-10-methyl-2 (1'-carbethoxy-ethylidene) decalin (III) was obtained in excellent yield after chromatography over alumina with petroleum ether-benzene (70 : 30).

*Eudesmane numbering⁷.

Lithium aluminium hydride reduction of this α , β -unsaturated ester(III) gave the corresponding allylic alcohol(IV) in 80 percent yield. This allylic alcohol (IV) was transformed into the title compound (I) by two different methods and in both cases the final product turned out to be the same as confirmed by I.R. and N.M.R. spectra. Alcohol(IV) was converted into corresponding bromide(V) in 68% yield with phosphoroutribromide in dry ether. The bromide(V) was submitted to reduction with sodium borohydride in dimethylsulphoxide⁵ to afford pure (t.l.c) hydrocarbon (I) in 92% yield after chromatography over alumina with petroleum ether as the eluent.

Alternatively, the allylic alcohol(IV) was submitted to hydrogenolysis⁶ with sodium ethanol in anhydrous liquid ammonia to afford pure (t.l.c.) (I) in 90% yield after chromatography over alumina with petroleum ether as the eluent. The identity of the hydrocarbon, in both cases, was established through the comparison of its I.R. and N.M.R. spectra with that reported¹ for the neutral selino-4(14),7(11)-diene.

Experimental

Boiling points are uncorrected. I.R. spectra were taken on Perkin Elmer 335 model using sodium chloride optics. N.M.R. spectrum was obtained on a Varian A60 spectrophotometer using tetramethylsilane as the internal standard.

Trans-8-Methylene-10-methyl-2(1'-carbethoxy-ethylidene) decalin(III) :

Sodium hydride (0.64 g) was placed in diglyme (50 ml) and ethyl α -diethyl phosphonopropionate (4.0 g) was added dropwise below 20° with stirring and the stirring continued till the complete evolution of the gas. To the resultant yellow solution was then added methylene ketone (II, 4.0 g) slowly below 10°. After addition, the solution was stirred for 2 hr and then warmed for half an hour at 50°. It was decomposed with large excess of water and extracted with ether (4×50 ml). The combined ether extracts were dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the solvent was removed. The residue was chromatographed over alumina (80 g) with petroleum ether-benzene (70 : 30) as the eluent followed by vacuum distillation to give (III, 3.2 g) in 73% yield; b.p. 130°-35°/4-5 mm; $\eta_D^{32} = 1.4473$. I.R. spectrum had characteristic absorption bands at 1725 cm^{-1} (conj. ester); 1650 and 890 cm^{-1} (methylene). (Found : C, 77.34; H, 9.58. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 77.82; H, 9.90%).

Trans-8-Methylene-10-methyl-2(1'-hydroxymethyl-ethylidene) decalin(IV) :

To a well stirred suspension of lithium aluminium hydride (0.5 g) in dry ether (200 ml) was added dropwise a solution of the ester (III, 3.0 g) in anhydrous ether (100 ml) keeping the reaction mixture in ice cold water. Stirring was continued for 3 hr at room temperature. The complex was then decomposed

with a saturated solution of sodium potassium tartarate and the hydrosylate was thoroughly extracted with ether. The ether extract was subsequently dried and the solvent expelled. The residue upon distillation under reduced pressure afforded the carbinol (IV, 1.76 g) in 80% yield; b.p. 120°-25°/3-4 mm; $\eta_D^{32} = 1.4901$. I.R. spectrum showed no absorption in carbonyl region and showed characteristic absorption peaks at 3350, 1045 cm^{-1} (hydroxy, -OH). (Found : C, 81.99; H, 10.50. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}$ requires C, 81.75; H, 10.98%).

Trans-8-Methylene-10-methyl-2(1'-bromomethyl ethylidene) decalin(V) :

A light protected solution of the carbinol (IV, 0.8 g) in dry ether (25 ml) was chilled in ice bath. To this was added dropwise phosphoroutribromide (0.56 g, 0.2 ml) in dry ether (2 ml). The reaction mixture was allowed to attain room temperature and was kept at a gentle reflux for 2 hr, cooled, decomposed with iced water (5 ml) and extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed successively with water, 5% sodium bicarbonate solution and dried. Evaporation of the solvent yielded (V, 0.65 g) in 65% yield. This bromide was not distilled and used as such for the next operation. I.T. spectrum showed no absorption in the hydroxy region.

Trans-8-Methylene-10-methyl-2-isopropylidene decalin(I)

(A) The bromide (V, 0.55 g) in anhydrous dimethylsulphoxide (2 ml) was slowly added to sodium borohydride (140 mg) in anhydrous dimethylsulphoxide (15 ml) at 18° during half an hour period and the colourless solution was stirred for an additional hour at 18°. The mixture was slowly added to cold 3N HCl, and the product was extracted with petroleum ether and dried. Evaporation of solvent followed by vacuum distillation yielded (I, 0.350 g) in 88% yield; b.p. 122°-26°/4-5 mm; $\eta_D^{32} = 1.4741$. T.l.c. showed single visible spot. ($R_f = 0.74$); solvent system : Benzene : Pet. ether (50 : 50).

(B) Sodium metal (1.0 g) was added in small pieces to a mixture of the allylic alcohol (IV, 0.75 g), absolute ethanol (15 ml) and anhydrous liquid ammonia (250 ml) with stirring. After the addition the stirring was continued for about 3 hr, whereafter the excess of ammonia was evaporated and the solid cake left behind was decomposed with ice cold water (100 ml). The resulting solution was extracted with ether and dried. After the solvent removal the residue was passed through alumina (30 g) and pure hydrocarbon was obtained on elution with petroleum ether. The solvent was removed and the hydrocarbon distilled under vacuum to secure (I, 0.66 g) in about 99% yield; b.p. 122°-25°/4-5 mm; $\eta_D^{32} = 1.4741$. T.l.c. showed single visible spot. ($R_f = 0.74$); solvent system : Benzene : Petroleum ether (50 : 50).

I.R. spectrum showed peaks at 2900, 1645, 1455, 1360, 890 cm^{-1} (S); 3055, 2700, 1755, 1400, 1270, 1250, 1220, 1165, 1145, 1130, 1100, 1090, 1080, 1040, 1020, 1000, 940, 850 and 795 cm^{-1} (weak and medium).

Literature¹ reports peaks at 1650, 1450, 1360, 890 cm^{-1} (S); 1755, 1400, 1260, 1255, 1225, 1170, 1160, 1130, 1100, 1095, 1080, 1045, 1020, 1000, 980, 940, 855 and 805 cm^{-1} (weak and medium). N.M.R. (CCl_4) $\delta = 0.8$ (3H); 4.7, 4.52(2H); 1.66 (6H). These are comparable to that reported in the literature¹.

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